

Focus groups 4: findings

(Q1 was an icebreaker so not included here)

2 Have you used dashboards for business intelligence in the past? Which ones and how?

Participants described a range of data sources including their own data, OAPEN and others. Tools included dashboards hosted by the organisation, external third parties; and tools such as Salesforce, Google Analytics, and Tableau. These were used for Informing decisions (though the volume of data and the lack of consistency in usage criteria limited its usefulness), understanding usage (including sharing this with authors), and troubleshooting the platform.

Data sources

- Own data
- Federating from others
 - OAPEN
 - EBSCO, OAPEN, website
 - OAPEN
 - OAPEN for content hosted on MUSE/OAPEN
- Someone else federating for us

Tools mentioned

- Self-hosted dashboard
- Externally hosted dashboard
 - OAPEN usage dashboard for MUSE/OAPEN content
 - seller shows what is ordered by smaller bookshops, development over time for single or group of titles
 - Proquest has amazing dashboard very usable for publishers to do research; KU dashboard when it's working
 - JSTOR, OAPEN, MUSE, UP Digital
 - Ingram, CoreSource, all associated with cost recovery and designed around sales. CoreSource doesn't know what to do with zero price points
 - proquest, JSTOR, Ingram lightning source
- Salesforce
- GoogleAnalytics
- Tableau

Used for

- Informing decisions
 - different vocab makes it difficult to align; consolidation's so massive they can't cope with the volume
 - incredible insights for development is marred by lack of consistency in usage criteria and different levels of data
- Understanding usage

- Sharing with authors
- Troubleshooting platform

3 What could you accomplish with these dashboards that would further your own efforts?

- **Informing publishing decisions**, such as publishing more in English. Some uncertainty about how to use the data that can be seen (*education opportunity about how the data can be used*)
- **Understanding usage**, such as which author/publisher how many downloads in how many countries, preferences for full books vs chapters.
 - “Our current articulation of OA is narrative-, not data-driven, so it's very labour intensive”
- **Sharing with authors, funders**. Frequent acknowledgement that numbers need to be delivered with “paragraphs of explanation” (*education opportunity to create reusable text for this purpose*). Wider goal of getting editorial boards, authors, and funders to understand OA investment - the main benefit would be having something tangible to show people. *As before, education opportunity to explain to authors and editors what usage actually means. And how to compare items that are not easily comparable - print and e, page reads to book downloads...*
 - “We use standard answers all the time because we don't have the full figures”
 - “Without paywall, usage data is most valuable because there is a level playing field, access based purely on the merits of the research.”
 - “I'd like to go to my funders and say look, here's what you're doing. Here's our activity dear Provost or dear benefactor.”
- **Troubleshooting platform**: maps and charts make it easier to see and also know if something's suspicious
- Nice quotes on a key value proposition of BAD - that it allows **easy synthesis and consolidation of the data sources**, which is otherwise very manual - having global view and aggregation, seeing wider swath of data and whole picture, being able to send and have data in real time
 - “Lot of work for me to prepare the information I could, info from aggregation (one off). Need synthesis, data exchange between systems to be sure nothing was off. 56 titles, missing platforms.”
 - “I don't have to coordinate my downloads on the same day at the same time. It'll make life a hell of a lot easier than going 10-15 places for the data”
 - “Drawing together data sources is really valuable”
 - “I want that torrent of usage, and the main screen is so powerful.”
- Opportunity for making **new sources** available to publishers - “Not everyone will give you metrics, for books don't get usage from big aggregators unless subscription, not for those sold with perpetual access.”
- **Requirements**: Has to be simple, run quickly, be assigned to intern. If onerous or complicated, not using it.

- Informing decisions
 - Based on numbers, we could adjust our policy, e.g. publish more in English
 - Publishing decisions et al, yeah. Acquiring editors often rely on instinct not data. If there was a torrent of data...obstacles to that. We do get JSTOR et al, but can't do much with it. We

have a mission to serve underserved fields. Temptation is to say tell me what works and we'll do more of that. Seeing data, not sure how we'd use it. 2.0 step maybe, would take several years of managing, visualising, sorting

- Understanding usage
 - Which author/publisher how many downloads in how many countries
 - Understanding how accessed, popularity
 - full books vs chapters, what's preferred
 - important to see what kind of impact research you publish has
 - Our current articulation of OA is narrative, not data driven, so it's very labour intensive
- Sharing with authors
 - authors, funders
 - hard to imagine delivering numbers without paragraphs of explanation
 - authors are interested in more comprehensive and coherent usage information
 - authors want to know how many people had a look at their book, simple and good to see how many and also where located, from which region, continent, etc.
 - Authors like to know how much books are downloaded and used.
 - also get editorial board, author, funder questions to understand OA investment, is it achieving the aim of a much larger reach. We use standard answers all the time because we don't have the full figures. Similar to what we see on Springer website, 20x more often read if OA. Would be so good to show real data title by title, but we get so many diff sources, and you can't lump them together. That would be the main benefit, something tangible to show people
 - authors and editors increasingly want to see impact their research is having on OA side of things; resource like this would be really important for journals as well. Use this data to supplement what we can say now about what faculty are getting in terms of impact and engagement. Missing piece of jigsaw for OA. Without paywall, usage data is most valuable because there is a level playing field, access based purely on the merits of the research. Being able to measure that usage, purest form of understanding (limiting factor now is how well we phrase questions to find answers or is the the availability of the data) Availability of the data, but think also needs to be education for authors and editors to explain what usage actually means
 - info about sales, but can't inform about free downloads about OA. Meeting yesterday with authors, they wanted to know how much their books were downloaded. Lot of work for me to prepare the information I could, info from aggregation (one off). Need synthesis, data exchange between systems to be sure nothing was off. 56 titles, missing platforms. How to compare page reads to book download, also crazy
 - This blends OA and traditional paywall/cost recovery channel. Seamlessly deliver info to authors on regular basis--log in and see their title, or I can run reports for them of pdfs or screenshots for their title
- Sharing with Funders
 - also get editorial board, author, funder questions to understand OA investment, is it achieving the aim of a much larger reach. We use standard answers all the time because we don't have the full figures. Similar to what we see on Springer website, 20x more often read if OA. Would be so good to show real data title by title, but we get so many diff sources, and you can't lump them together. That would be the main benefit, something tangible to show people
 - Institutions are not just looking at what usage is for journal output, eg talking to Lunge and they want to know usage across the board for journals and books.

- I'd like to go to my funders and say look, here's what you're doing. Here's our activity dear Provost or dear benefactor.
- Troubleshooting platform
 - #s are reliable, are they real numbers. Maps and charts make it easier to see and also know if something's suspicious
- Getting multiple sources at once
 - OA live in different places and accessed different ways, having global view and aggregation
 - Seeing wider swath of data and whole picture
 - Being able to send and have data in real time, don't have to coordinate my downloads on the same day at the same time. It'll make life a hell of a lot easier than going 10-15 places for the data
 - Incomplete, don't have all sources so you don't have the full picture
 - Drawing together data sources is really valuable
 - By using this tool, stats from several sources.
 - huge advantage in one stop, one app where you find data for diff sources. Let's remember to look at this source, this source, and this source right now. Option to input usage data into google scholar/analytics, that gives a point of entry to consolidate. Combine the data always trouble, always a bit different
 - Getting multiple at once, one stop, consolidation
- New sources
 - Sources we don't currently have; OA books
 - Not everyone will give you metrics, for books don't get usage from big aggregators unless subscription, not for those sold with perpetual access.
- Requirements
 - author view, staff view, funder view, tick boxes or not to answer fundamental questions
 - Has to be simple, run quickly, be assigned to intern. If onerous or complicated, not using it

4 Which features are essential and which are desirable? Why?

Participants thought many if not all the features were essential and struggled to relegate any to "desirable".

Essential

- Comparing like with like: Essential that metrics from different platforms tally, accurate data
- Download data and images/maps/elements. Many appreciated having both pdf and xls/csv options as these were used for different purposes (image for sharing with authors or colleagues; data export for further analysis)
- Interactive: click charts to analyse info, break it down and look at it in different ways (e.g. Event Data, Wikipedia vs Crossref, compare what's going on in different locations)
- Quick/straightforward; doesn't take extra work to figure out what numbers mean; ease of use
- Standardised metrics
- Easy to add new sources
- Download images/elements

- Filtering options
 - Filter out noise, Google or whatever crawlers
 - Filter by series and then compare books within a series and their usage base
 - Filtering options are really essential. Country, title, ISBN, funder, topic/subject
- Notifications: email me a report, an automated weekly email that says these are your top performing downloads
- Integration into my website - "Would also love to integrate the dashboard into my website like U of M"

Desirable

- want to add journals, desirable but not essential
- Know how many users move from page view to actually download the content

Usability

- Font/size issues
 - Some text is very small to read. Country labels and book titles don't scale up on the computer
 - There's more below the fold: Found dashboard upper type for mobile phone great, but we usually work on standard computers and the whole screen full of large numbers and only on 2nd or 3rd view did I see specific data below
- General ignorance of Crossref Event Data - *opportunity for more education on what this is (including hover-over info in the interface?)*

- Comparing like with like
 - Essential that metrics from different platforms tally
 - accurate data
 - accurate numbers
 - comparable studies within OA. AND institution-wise, very important, authors want specific usage by their institution
- Download data
 - need to download, do things with data beyond dashboard
 - Publisher can consolidate and incorporate with other data they have
 - export. In some instances only pdf, really appreciate having xls as well both for manipulating and for using in presentations
- Quick/straightforward
 - show to authors; show to funders, people really using, you should fund us
 - doesn't take extra work to figure out what numbers mean
 - ease of use
- Standardised metrics
 - make the standards obvious and easy to understand
 - city level, geolocation
- easy to add new sources
 - Like bibliovault, easy to add new vendor/repository/etc
 - want to add journals, desirable but not essential
- Download images/elements
 - download map, images to present

- click charts to analyse info, break it down and look at it in different ways (eg event data, wikipedia vs Crossref compare what's going on in different locations)
- Being able to download would be essential for certain kinds of reporting, eg authors using in P&T folders
- KU analytics tool, can download on basis of title comparison from different platforms, I can screenshare one of these PDF (OAPEN, jstor, open research library mixed in KU and you can see by platform-)
- Also want map! (jpeg)
- how would you tell me to share results of search with somebody. Can I export screenshot as pdf, or ... yeah, it would be helpful to send to marketing director. I don't want to tell him to go to the dashboard, I want to send him the results. (you can download the data)
- Font/size issues
 - some text very small to read. Mobile design. Like country labels and book titles, doesn't scale up on the computer, proportions.
 - Found dashboard upper type for mobile phone great, but we usually work on standard computers and the whole screen full of large numbers and only on 2nd or 3rd view did I see specific data below
- Filtering options
 - who's downloading from where, seems always the US is exceptionally large in usage, even for Dutch language stuff, I always think this is something else going on. Would be very important to filter out noise, Google or whatever crawlers.
 - encounter a lot with funders/authors on OA projects, book is part of a series. Never been able to select a series and then compare books within a series and their usage base. Select series and see projects within that
 - filtering options are really essential. Country, title, I had quick look at dashboard, always want to filter on ISBN, I love the country map, really relevant. I know with OA there's always the funder but funder info would be very nice but I'm not sure how transparent that is For instance, using Dimensions. Filter for big funder, what research have they funded. More and more, requests from institutes, want to know distribution, if possible to have funder info though I admit that's very detailed...or topic, see within a topical area
 - downloads and page views. How many are actually wanting to get that content, how many move from page view to actually download it
 - Only thing I didn't know how to apply is Crossref event data. Interesting, unlike some of the other tabs that I know exactly how to use/share, I wouldn't know what this means, when authors come back with questions I don't know what I could tell them. (especially depending on their field, take at face value or debate it with you. Just so you know what it is, Crossref social media monitoring, measure of how much people are talking about a book or chapter on those platforms)
 - book and chapter data separated; could you have numerous filters, like which books on public policy are big in Canada or something like that
- Other
 - Everything here is essential.
 - email me a report, like if I could just get an automated weekly email that says these are your top performing downloads; Would also love to integrate the dashboard into my website like U of M

5 What features are we currently missing that you feel are important?

Feature requests

- **Sticky select:** “have a page you can select on global reach, go through and see the other info on that book only if I reselect multiple times, want to see everything on that book all at once” (match up across features so you don’t have one book on global reach and another on another topic at the same time)
- **Multi-select:** show me all data for Great Britain **and** Ireland. Or all John Smith **and** John Miller
- Select **timeframe**, year or month
- Search and **drill-down:** regional or use ISO standards (states in US for example); ability to drill down to book title level data for the sub filters (currently you don't know which books it's referring to if you search on the Subject or Author tabs); Title per country (which books are used in each country?); more specific geolocation, city data
- **Publisher identification:** how many books a publisher/aggregator is contributing.
- **Publisher filter:** can you add which platforms activities happened on?
- **White labelling:** branding on top part.
- **Export:** CSV download
- **Provenance information, data quality guarantee:** Legend/FAQ/something to hover over to understand how BAD defines these terms and what you’re tracking, what usage means. *Opportunity to reassure about COUNTER-compliant data and use of ISO standard re: geography, etc).* Like Champagne, have a [protected designation of origin](#)
- Include **journals**
- **Subject BISAC filters** currently add different levels of granularity e.g. ‘HSS’ or ‘Science’ compared to ‘Computers’
- **Integration into my own website** like U of Mich

Possible bugs/small tweaks

- **Select functionality:** “I’ve gone to the filter, clicked on it, defaults to everything, so I had to intuitively know to unselect.... Move outside search box, need prompt like “go”, a checkout button”
- **Select all/select one:** searched for John and couldn’t select one John... a better view of your filters would help (show what I’ve selected, like online shopping)
- **Reset button:** took a while to find reset button
- **Last name/first name [or family name/given name]** - what’s the order used?
- **ISBN search**
- **ORCID**
- **Columns clearly labelled** (marking of dates on x axis), use year quarters instead of months if space is tight?

- Feature request
 - Sticky select
 - multi-select, show me all data for Great Britain and Ireland. Or all John Smith and John Miller, stuff like that.
 - I think it might be useful if you have a page you can select on global reach, go through and see the other info on that book only if I reselect multiple times, want to

see everything on that book all at once (sticky select - match up across features so you don't have one book on global reach and another on another topic at the same time

- I've gone to the filter, clicked on it, defaults to everything, so I had to intuitively know to unselect. Then you click on something and nothing really happens--you have to click away and wait for refresh. Need a go button or something like that. Felt a little lost there. There's a little "only" box that populates on the right, don't know what that's doing. Doesn't look like it matters if I click it or not. (if you're browsing the whole list, you then can click "only" next to one of those titles). Instead of being able to choose multiple titles, ok. That's not obvious to me. Once I realised I could click on one or multiple titles, I didn't need something to tell me this was the only one I've clicked on. Move outside search box, need prompt like "go", a checkout button
- Select timeframe
 - eg, book mostly used in China in pandemic, really interesting to see that was a top book there at that time when we had made the books open
 - to select certain time period should be very easy to do, year or month, time frame. Should be super easy to find, may already be one
- Search and drill-down
 - regional or use ISO standards (states in US for example)
 - ability to drill down to book title level data for the sub filters (currently you don't know which books it's referring to if you search on the Subject or Author tabs)
- Title per country
 - If I pick Chad, it has aggregate usage, but can I drill down and see what books are used in each country?
 - more specific geolocation, city data
- Publisher inclusion
 - how many books a publisher is contributing. So you can see 30% is OUP and understand where it's coming from, or how many are diff aggregators adding in so you get idea of what's in there
 - Mentioning which publishers are included within the data -- currently it doesn't explain how comprehensive this data set is, or if it's relevant to the person using it.
- White labelling
 - White-label branding on top part. Dashboard would say "U of Michigan Press" or what have you.
- Other
 - Couldn't find the publishers. Aggregating for authors, but couldn't find publishers
 - CSV download
 - Can you add which platforms activities happened on? Publisher filter?
 - benefit from not a dictionary but (legend?) when we worked on our OA project, what we were measuring was hard to name, faq or something to hover over to understand how you define these terms and what you're tracking, what usage means. JSTOR/MUSE have different meanings to "usage". Sentence or two somewhere (reassure COUNTER data or ISO standard re: geography, etc). Back to the definitional thing - different colour tab, still describe, for authors, that's coded. You are letting your own org define. Still need overview about, don't assume. (champagne as corollary) Also, an FAQ would be useful to have on the dashboard.
 - Add journals
- Possible Bugs/small tweaks

- Select all/select one
 - Small thing I found, not really feature, but searched for John and couldn't select one John. (bug) Can't tell if I really selected just one (John Smith) UX thing rather than data thing, but better view of your filters would help. Like shirt, xl and red, see that you've selected those things
 - have one select all at the top or How to select one or more titles is a bit confusing
- Reset button
 - Took a while to find reset button
- Last name/first name
 - first name and then second name. Lots of Andrews, but if I don't know first name I'm lost. Carl Risking, not Risking, Carl
- ISBN search
 - ISBN search because some books have same title (DOIs)
 - ISBN search for titles
- ORCID
 - ORCID agreement (suggested by Laura to this group)
 - ORCID of authors is important
 - ORCID/PID standardisation
- Columns clearly labelled
 - monthly access and Crossref data, hard time tying diagonal dates to the columns. Doesn't look like every column has a date associated. Hard to identify (answering our question from pre-work), hovering, visually struggled. (if you hover, can you see it?) Yes--but didn't see that before. Diagonal looks like every 2-3 months, a little random (space and x axis, just doesn't all show) Might use quarterly time markers as default instead of what looks a little random
- Other
 - Subject BISAC filters currently add different levels of granularity e.g. 'HSS' or 'Science' compared to 'Computers' (are books included in more than one category).
 - Integration into my own website like U of Mich

6 Who from your team will be the primary user(s) of the dashboards?

Will be users

- Director
- Sales/Marketing/Communications
- Acquiring editors/editorial team
- Authors - but there is widespread concern that this needs to be done with great care and guidance - "this is what it means, don't panic".
 - Some disagree and do not plan to involve authors - "authors have different expectations, sometimes not very realistic. Therefore, I think it would cause problems to give full access to authors, compare their book with another book with completely other circumstances for example."

- OA publishing unit
- Finance/Business analyst
- Operations/Program Manager

Will NOT be users

- Funders
- Public (via publisher's website) - but some want to have their dashboard on their website

- Director
 - one is publisher himself and he will def be the one in charge
- Sales/Marketing
 - Sales team for sales prospecting. If a lot of OA Spanish books are being used somewhere might be able to use that for sales prospecting.
 - Same as [name redacted] (sales for prospecting)
 - Yes
 - marketing because need to measure marketing against usage. And myself (sales manager)
 - acquiring editors and marketing team might both potentially use it. I want to be super candid though that this would be a leap. All would be intrigued, but battle making OA safe for UPs. So much prejudice. I want to overwhelm their prejudice with user data. Even if they're substandard books, they're getting used more in this specific way. I want that torrent of usage, and the main screen is so powerful. Using data to make publishing decisions isn't the problem I'm trying to solve right now. I want to easily display how much OA books get used.
 - marketing and comms person
- Acquiring Editors
 - publisher relations would be acquisition strategies
 - add editorial team as well for OA books because they will want to give this data to authors or use it to provide reports to them
 - commissioning editors should be using this in their convos with authors/editors
 - Yes
 - yes, and another colleague
 - acquiring editors and marketing team might both potentially use it. I want to be super candid though that this would be a leap. All would be intrigued, but battle making OA safe for UPs. So much prejudice. I want to overwhelm their prejudice with user data. Even if they're substandard books, they're getting used more in this specific way. I want that torrent of usage, and the main screen is so powerful. Using data to make publishing decisions isn't the problem I'm trying to solve right now. I want to easily display how much OA books get used.
- Authors
 - NO - Concern--this is great and useful for publisher, I'll have to do explaining to authors, this is what it means don't panic.
 - NO - Extra output for non-publisher users. In what way can I convey to admin and authors and in what form? They cannot access these kinds of dashboards I presume
 - No - authors have diff expectations, sometimes not very realistic. Therefore, I think it would cause problems to give full access to authors, compare their book with another book with completely other circumstances for example. So having one sight (view) for one book, or we will restrict to just ourselves and then we'll communicate numbers to authors with explanation
 - No - we would massage before handing to authors, this would just be for us

- Funders
 - NO - And those that count the money and sit in the offices will require a hell of a lot of explaining. Need more administrative gearing maybe
- Digital Publisher
 - Me on epublication
 - YES - primarily me because I oversee the OA stuff, the arrangements and production as well as metadata produced
- Public
 - No - other thing is how I can present nucleus of that info on my publishers website, in what form can I give to the public. Often very varied publishing pages with all kinds of metrics that are bells and whistles, fancy but not useful.
- OA Publishing Unit
 - add editorial team as well for OA books because they will want to give this data to authors or use it to provide reports to them
 - OA publishing unit will use to get key figures
 - colleague occupied with OA as well, he and I would be primary users
- Finance/Business analyst
 - business analyst who would create reports
 - Same as [name redacted] (business analyst)
 - maybe also finance dept if they can get figures to feed into their own dashboards
- Operations/Program Manager
 - plus program manager also
 - operations team member who pulls all of the usage data for all of our partners on monthly basis
 - manager
- Me [10 participants]
- Other
 - 6 people
 - me and 1-2 others (specific to their role? Or small team so everyone?) Role and everyone, yes
 - I'd like our whole team of 6 to be able to use it

7 If we build a standard/premium or standard/à la carte model, what belongs in each?

Premium features

- Different opinions on whether **data** is standard and **download graphs** is premium, or the other way around
- **API**
- **Integrations**
 - into your webpage to show some type of data (or widget)
 - with another tool, Salesforce or other
- Being able to add more **data sources**

- Amazon data
- Institutional repository data, where the press has unique distribution nodes, or the author has a website?
- **Multiple views** (publisher/librarian/author)
- **Deeper look** (e.g., not just region, but town), being able to drill down to city-level data
- **Performance by subject area** across publishers, track how our title is performing against others
- **Non-OA content**
- **A more detailed report** behind every number
- **Compare** our usage against other publishers
- **Custom reporting**

À la carte features

- **Add different ONIX streams** to integrate data from different platforms (à la carte because that takes additional time/energy from the tech team)

Standard features

- **Uses on book/chapter/paper**
- **Overview numbers** in the top banner - Standard could be limited to that.
- Argument against **downloadable data** as premium service? - Would expect data to be shared so we wouldn't expect an invoice for the data

On use of **competitive intelligence**, sharing data about multiple publishers

- "I wouldn't be protective about any usage or any content that is not financial; this shouldn't be secretive."
- "Are other publishers protective about their usage data for OA? I wouldn't be..."
- "If I were willing to have my data exposed/used/anonymized, give discount? Not selling the data but selling controlled access to its aggregation. I like the idea of you all seeing value in us exposing the data."

Does this contradict earlier point from question 3 about a key value proposition of BAD - that it allows easy synthesis and consolidation of the data sources, which is otherwise very manual - "Drawing together data sources is really valuable"?

Other

- Difficulties with **comparing books**, understanding why one gets loads of downloads and another doesn't - *education opportunity*. Could be a particular issue for publishers with smaller number of title - harder to see a pattern

- Premium features
 - Premium with custom features that I ask for
 - premium could be even more luxury...sometimes you need just once a year, special aggregation one time.
 - Being able to download graphs might be premium. Someone smarter than me might be able to DIY it but for those of us who really want to just grab and use, premium
 - I was thinking the opposite of what [name] said, premium to get the data
 - being able to use API for your own site; quite difficult to select premium/standard without knowing whole option, but personalised dashboard or everyone view general offer; do you

use it outside of the platform, is it something you can integrate into your webpage to show some type of data (or widget)

- Agree being able to use API for your own site
- being able to offer more data sources or being able to add OS data into your own dashboard so you can merge things together; premium should be tailored to individual institution? Or give multiple views (publisher/librarian/author)? Holistic view of all vs specific aspect of it.
- "integration with another tool, Salesforce or otherwise, export data via API. Not everyone will want that, so premium; also ability to isolate data on particular thing, like Crossref twitter event data. Deeper explanation might be more premium.
- premium/a la carte could add download options or deeper look (e.g., not just region, but town) and more concrete info
- performance by subject area across publishers, not identifying a specific publisher, track how our title is performing against how others in a collective community are performing
- is this OA only (not necessarily, some publishers want to see non OA as well-premium?)
- Here's a more detailed report behind every number. That would be the premium info you would offer next to the more generic numbers.
- want to look at non-[publisher] books as well, value in paying for data that lets us compare our usage against other publishers (so far, thinking about having only your own titles rather than those from other publishers). Interesting to see how these perform across different publishers.
- Manipulating data for example. Being able to compare my open history monographs to collective similar publications. Can Amazon data be integrated? eg, CSV once a quarter? Or IR data, where the press has unique distribution nodes, or the author has a website? Charge for integration
- premium could include things like custom reporting, exporting to excel or other formats, being able to drill down to city-level data, I wouldn't know how to work with downloaded data but it would be amazing to have the option because we have people who know how to do that, like for annual reports or generate our own graphs depending on what's a hot topic at the time; stats emails like ScholarOne does for journals
- à la carte features
 - one version as basic info, and then I want to add different ONIX streams to integrate data from different platforms, could that be an option? A la carte most likely because that takes additional time/energy from the tech team.
 - I wouldn't know how to decide on a la carte right now.
- Standard features
 - As luxury as possible
 - It's hard to make sense of the data we have, so I look at our download data, I'll see comparable books, one gets loads of downloads and another doesn't or one gets lots of twitter and the other doesn't and I can't tell why, maybe data problems. I don't trust the data enough to try to ask it questions there. For larger publishers with thousands of titles, might be able to see pattern rather than assume fluke. For us, the dashboards are nice to have but may not inform us a lot because of #s of publications being smaller.
 - everyone likes to know how many uses on book/chapter/paper, and also where people came from, so that might be the standard
 - numbers you have in your top banner, those are interesting but generic. Standard limited to that.

- At [publisher], we use visualisation. We would want to download and incorporate into the dashboards we have. More sense to integrate (KS downloadable data as premium service?) Would expect data to be shared so we wouldn't expect an invoice for the data
- The more whole the data, the better.
- What's here as the top level data now - log in, select a book and it gives you the numbers. Maybe you could save as pdf.
- Other Notes
 - library publishers, also a different set of needs potentially
 - (on use of competitive intelligence, sharing data about multiple publishers) I wouldn't be protective about any usage or any content that is not financial; this shouldn't be secretive.
 - (on use of competitive intelligence, sharing data about multiple publishers) are other publishers protective about their usage data for OA? I wouldn't be...
 - (on use of competitive intelligence, sharing data about multiple publishers) If I were willing to have my data exposed/used/anonymized, give discount? \$2kYear for this, but only \$1500/year if you let your data go into the composite. Not selling the data but selling controlled access to its aggregation. I like the idea of you all seeing value in us exposing the data. Folks at MUSE, I push them, they say that's the press's data, not our data.

8 What pricing range would you expect for the service?

Ideas for pricing

There is consensus that there should not be a flat fee for all publishers, but beyond that, a range of possible solutions are suggested. Some participants envisage BAD as an add-on or supplement to OAPEN membership; others think it should be included in that.

- Tiered, banded
- Per (OA?) title fee (keep this within the cost for each book)
- No to per-title fee
- BAD as an add-on to existing OAPEN membership. Could be related to OAPEN membership levels or a supplement to OAPEN fee rather than stand alone cost
- By number of downloads

Current willingness to pay

Few publishers are currently willing to pay, but it was widely acknowledged that there will be a need for this usage data a few years into the future and that there are currently no alternative sources for it.

- No, but it will be different in 5 years' time (driven by demands from stakeholders)
- No, it is outsourcing something we currently do internally.
- No, at the moment I wouldn't pay anything for it... It would have to be less than OAPEN membership
- No, numbers aren't complete because partners can still be added, still only shows part of the usage and part of the story.

Dollar amount

Few publishers were willing to name an amount they would be prepared to pay. This may reflect the current lack of commercial activity in this area (and therefore publishers knowing what to expect) rather than a lack of enthusiasm for the service.

- Could start open [free] and then restrict [require payment] after, once the service is established
- Look at not-quite-competitors doing something similar, altmetrics, dimensions?
- Goal is to be open in 5 years, so standard USD \$5-10K year at that point... \$10K might include training (or videos) in how to use analytics et al. Is there a start-up charge or initial investment? And then per-product, like \$2K for start and \$25 per title or something like that, so that it grows as your titles grow? Start up costs for training and credentials. Initial first year charge for that piece? Counter the one-time onboarding expense

Timeframe needed

This depends on the pricing of the service and the size of the organisation. Generally speaking, the cheaper the price and the smaller the organisation, the faster a decision can be made.

- Tiered
 - I'd suggest tiered pricing, small UP vs large profitable press, probably shouldn't pay the same, esp given different scale of content in there. UPs are categorised by annual revenues, maybe have non-profit and for-profit publisher ranges.
 - banding, yes, that might make sense. Important thing around equity and not having it be a financial hurdle for people.
 - I was thinking about flat price for all participants, or would you have one price for small publishers, one for UPs
 - tiered rate for size and earned revenue
 - Australian Publishing Assoc, break it down by turnover the year before; you could even have more than 2 tiers
- Per-Title fee
 - pricing for this, not going to mention the African situation and discount we'd expect. Here, it's a service with a product application. Would try to keep this within the cost for each book, like ONIX records. Figure this into cost per book for the press. That might be one way to do this, and that would work out well for UPs who don't have a lot of OA. That might be a way to do it. Mixed model of pricing, not just # of titles or size, but something in between.
 - amount of OAPEN books published per year, more OA you'll profit more from the dashboard?
 - Does it make a difference how many titles a publisher is accessing? (not a difference to how much work it takes to run the service) Eg our community of publishers, number of ways to slice up the community. Revenue, #titles/year, and maybe what grouping within the publisher is applied here (e.g., a publisher may only have a small set of OA books even if they're a huge publisher)
 - staying away from a per-title fee which is what a lot of platforms are using, those are very pissy.
- OAPEN tag on
 - service from OAPEN, so if publisher is a member, is it an addition you can apply to membership? Should be related to OAPEN membership levels. Supplement to OAPEN fee rather than stand alone
- By Downloads
 - The obvious one to me seems to be downloads because those are the statistics you'd essentially be paying to get aggregated reports on. A small publisher might publish quite a few books but not get traction and it would not be fair for them to pay as much as a publisher putting out the same number of books but getting less traction

- Would pay
 - I think pricing would be dependent upon internal resources, and I don't know what's being spent at [publisher] internally to get this view of usage compared to price of service. It is outsourcing something we currently do internally.
 - No version of this we could currently afford to pay for. 5 years from now, that will no longer be the case, will need to satisfy external reports so I know this is shortsighted (changes that would alter the situation is demands from stakeholders?) Yes, absolutely that's the factor driving it.
- Wouldn't pay
 - At the moment I wouldn't pay anything for it, I don't see the whole picture so hard to say how much our institution would pay for it. It would have to be less than OAPEN membership or it would be very difficult to state to our superiors re: we have membership but the service costs more.
 - initial reaction was it looks really good but numbers aren't complete because partners can still be added, SciELO, EBSCO, Clarivate. Still only shows part of the usage and part of the story. In order to create whole picture, work needs to happen internally. Doesn't mean it's the place to go to get your usage yet.
 - right now, we wouldn't pay for this. Demand for the data right now wouldn't justify a specific outlay of annual fee. Clunky and cumbersome to gather this data myself, but I can do it and it's been good enough so far. Book side of SS and Humanities aren't as demanding as other disciplines re: reporting. Not coming from authors or funders in any specific way. Very infrequent questions from authors. No version of this we could currently afford to pay for.
- Dollar amount
 - As for a dollar amount, I don't know.
 - could start open and then restrict after, once the service is established. Somehow you have to establish, how to get the first couple hundred or thousand subscribers. Have to be very clear about what you get, possibilities to start with totally open and hope it's so good that people will start paying. Examples of services like that, youtube and things like that either, where slowly/gradually you want to pay (premium, removal of annoyances like advertising)
 - no idea what it should cost
 - Look at not-quite-competitors doing something similar, altmetrics, dimensions?
 - Don't have enough titles yet to feel this is a must-have but the goal is to be open in 5 years, so standard USD \$5-10K year at that point. Right now, that would be supporting-you money, I wouldn't get \$5K worth yet, but this would be a contribution to help you get there. \$1-2k/year, I'd get my checkbook out right now, especially if I can share with authors. \$5K doesn't get you kicked out of the room, \$10K might include training (or videos) in how to use analytics et al. Is there a start-up charge or initial investment? And then per-product, like \$2K for start and \$25 per title or something like that, so that it grows as your titles grow? Start up costs for training and credentials. Initial first year charge for that piece? Counter the one-time onboarding expense
 - need to talk to the team and get back to you, probably come from marketing budget, we know it's not going to be free and we do get benefits from it, so we'd have to decide premium/basic. I can't even give you a range
- Timeframe needed?
 - amount of time will depend on pricing; also, if subscription it'll take longer
 - University presses have the unhelpful answer that it entirely depends on the idiosyncratic purchasing rules of any given university administration!
 - if price is ok, can decide it very quick

- timeframe depends on price. Not long, weeks
- relationship between pricing and who gets to decide. If it's a million, I can't decide.
- If a couple thousand dollars, no lead time at all

9 Who from your team will be involved in the signing of legal agreements?

Director
Publisher
Editor

Other

- editorial services would sign with the legal dept
- Open access books lead
- [name], the librarian, because we sit under her
- legal council at [publisher] would advise; CPO and VP sales to agree
- I would imagine we'd be looking at a similar business/pricing model to something like OA Switchboard; business case presented to [press's] Senior Management Team

Director

- managing director
- Director of publishing relations and content development
- Director of the press
- [press's] director, [name], but I'd be the one to go through and negotiate; probably not have to go to [press's] Legal (which would take up to 6 months lead time)
- press director
- Director of academic publishing
- me (director)
- [name]
- ED

Publisher

- Publisher
- Chief publishing officer

Editor

- me (editor) and publisher
- me (editor) and publisher head
- managing editor

It depends

- Each data source might require a different sign off. Is there a separate agreement for each? new territory, don't know precisely who should sign, who feels most appropriate
- depends on cost and recurrent nature of cost
- press director for most UPs, but others might be sales or OA publisher or marketing director

Other

- editorial services would sign with the legal dept
- Open access books lead
- [name], the librarian, because we sit under her
- legal council at [publisher] would advise; CPO and VP sales to agree
- I would imagine we'd be looking at a similar business/pricing model to something like OA Switchboard; business case presented to [press's] Senior Management Team

10 What community governance qualities or characteristics would you want and expect for this service?

Governance and involvement level

Many publishers were **reluctant to commit to being involved**: whether for simple reasons of time, competition with other community engagement commitments, and also because they were wary of not feeling sufficiently well-informed or keeping up with developments.

There was a preference for **consultative rather than democratic** engagement with BAD governance. "I am always happy if things run without soliciting me too much. Good to have the opportunity to provide feedback but if you think the nicest services, those run smoothly and you don't have to interact with them."

Publishers like an **annual meeting model** to keep them informed. The Crossref member vote model was appreciated but some respondents acknowledged that they didn't take part in the elections. "With Crossref we can choose the board members. I find it nice and charming but I'm a bit lost, I don't know those persons, it gives me the feeling I should be involved but it's a farce. I would rather be able to give my opinion and that's enough." *Non-participation of this kind could really hamper our activities if we adopt a participative democracy model but the electorate don't vote and therefore we can't progress with our projects or strategy.*

In terms of **community governance**, publishers thought that authors, scholars, university presses, and publishers should have more of a say; librarians and universities less so. Funders might also be a key voice. It was acknowledged that smaller orgs might not be able to represent themselves as well because of lower staffing.

Being part of a **community around OA books usage data** is appealing to publishers - sharing success stories, difficulties, and support - without the responsibility of governance. An annual report and stakeholder meetings were suggested, which could include technical developments, trends in usage, communicating the upcoming technical roadmap, opportunity to make suggestions. Project MUSE Meets sessions were given as an example of good practice.

Feature requests/tech roadmap

This idea is welcomed by publishers: being able to make suggestions, see what others have contributed, and upvote ideas. There was a caveat: "publishers might not have a lot of good insight about what's

technically feasible; the technical team can see what's computationally possible/impossible." Participants did not think that governance should include decision-making about technology - "We can make suggestions, but should not fly the plane."

Data rights protected, not sold or used without permission

For publishers, it was important that this data is provided in trust, not sold on, and is only used appropriately. They wanted to know who would have access to the dashboard, which organisations can see which aspects, and that any planned change in use of data would need to be checked with them before being implemented. "I don't trust big tech - too many potential misuses. Mitigate, control against that." Publishers wanted to know which country/regional rules (jurisdiction) would apply to BAD data. Some were concerned about how the community of scholars and authors would be impacted when this data is used, and that publishers/librarians/book industry might not see this in the same way that a scholarly career would.

Transparency is key: knowing which publishers are involved so that we know how holistic this data is, is it all books or a subset; "making clear the universe of the BAD project".

The **not-for-profit status** of this service was important to publishers, particularly the "bright line around the inability to sell this to someone."

OAPEN as governance

Many publishers were happy with the idea of BAD becoming an OAPEN service under OAPEN's existing governance - "yes, we are very happy with OAPEN and how you do your job and work with us and we trust you and that sounds very good." They appreciated the streamlining of "piggy-back on an existing structure, not setting up something completely new."

However, a few voices raised concerns about bundling - whether the OAPEN service would then become more expensive once BAD is integrated. Respondents wanted to retain BAD as an independent transaction option, not just "this is free if you're an OAPEN member". They thought this separation between OAPEN services and the BAD service should remain at least until service maturity, to retain transparency about where money for the BAD goes (should go to the BAD service and not be used to cross-subsidise OAPEN).

- data rights protected, not sold or used without permission
 - data provided in trust, not sold on and is only used appropriately. Knowing who will have access to the dashboard, who can view it (what orgs see what aspects); any planned change in use of data would need to be checked before happening. t I don't trust big tech - too many potential misuses. Mitigate, control against that. Which rules apply to it - Europe? US? Wild west in lots of places including South Africa. Factor that in, part of discussion. Geographic/regional idiosyncrasies plus what regulations and rules can be put in place and how do we hold folks accountable.
 - knowing what #s are, community of scholars and authors impacted if data used, if there might be challenges, uses, problems that publishers/librarians/book industry might not see in the same way as a scholarly career would.
- Transparency
 - we need to know what publishers are involved so that we know how holistic this data is, is it all books or a subset. Making clear the universe of the "BAD" project

- OAPEN as governance
 - developed by OAPEN but might be disconnected later? (Laura clarifies, actually becoming more connected to OAPEN)
 - piggy-back on existing structure, not set up something completely new. And I am always happy if things run without soliciting me too much. Good to have opp to provide feedback but if you think the nicest services, those run smoothly and you don't have to interact with them.
 - if it's going to be part of OAPEN, is OAPEN governance in charge? Crossref service for Publishers, chooses the director and things like that (one member, one vote).
 - yes, we are very happy with OAPEN and how you do your job and work with us and we trust you and that sounds very good
 - nodding at [name], in favour of OAPEN
 - happy for OAPEN to take upon themselves this role of governance. WE've always had a good relationship with them
 - Danger is the bundling. What if you no longer offer a single thing, but only as integrated service. Don't want it to become more expensive, use this lucrative thing to subsidise less lucrative things. Would want to always have an independent transaction option, not just "this is free if you're an OAPEN member" as efficient as possible. Separation between OAPEN services and the BAD service, at least until service maturity. Transparency about where money for the service goes (should go to the service and not OAPEN)
 - Lean more towards this, it's a service that we will pay for and get access to and I don't necessarily feel the need to be involved in the governing of it; time it takes to be involved, I'd rather have a trustworthy organisation running it
- community governance
 - Crossref, can choose board members. I find it nice and charming but I'm a bit lost, I don't know those persons, it gives me the feeling I should be involved but it's a farce. Would rather be able to give my opinion and that's enough. Annual collection of the data as the other piece, eg Crossref gives regular updates so I know what's happening, look in depth but at my own choosing
 - authors and publishers more of a say, librarians less so. Universities, too, might have input there. This is not COUNTER for example. It doesn't have that organisational focus
 - funder might also be a key voice. Have a stake in it. Maybe quantitative/qualitative research on that; careful with representation, smaller orgs might not be able to represent themselves as well, lower staffing, hard to balance when not 1:1
 - representation in community gov from author/scholar community, particularly when looking over TOME and reading over what they want to see and the reasons careerwise they want to see those.
 - agree with Irene, consultative, not democratic
 - consultative, not democratic
 - I don't want to be just a customer, at the same time, we are oversolicited so maybe just to be able to have one time a year to meet and be informed as a democratic way of deciding on evolution etc. (Crossref, all members encouraged to vote in the election) I went last year but not enough time to stay for the whole thing. (Other side, we put in so much work to make it possible for everyone to participate and still) Yes, it's my fault, it is great that you've made it possible
 - I don't feel compelled that my org has to be represented, though I'd like UPs to be at the table/representatives in a governing/oversight group.
- nonprofit status

- quality important to our mission is the non-profit status. As far as input, having annual update/webinar/opportunity for feedback, breakout rooms, annual survey, feel connected and if they're paying for the service, have influence
- Bright lines around the inability to sell this to someone
- Community building
 - more and more wanting success stories, difficulties, etc - as much as you can bring library/publishers together around making OA successful, that community building around support, smart to build that around this tool
 - as part of governance, have annual report to show the tech developments, what usage looks like overall on the platform, identifying trends. That would provide a way of communicating what the tech roadmap is for next 12 months, tie that in also with annual meeting, either at preexisting conference or zoom, review what's been happening, what developments on platform, offer option for partner publishers to actually suggest items they want to discuss or areas where they'd like opportunities to explore developments on the platform. (who would decide what to press forward with and prioritise) OOpen or whoever the governing body is. Project MUSE meets sessions are very much about developments with MUSE but also inviting stakeholders to suggest areas to explore. Have to be done very well in advance of any meeting or report so assess in terms of feasibility, demand for those developments
- Feature requests/tech roadmap
 - would like to make feature requests and maybe upload or view other feature requests (see what publishers want what). I think that how those, which of those are implemented and how, the publishers might not have a lot of good insight about what's tech feasible, tech team can see what's computationally possible/impossible. To what extent "governance" would include decision making about tech -- RE: TechnicalRoadmap input, Make suggestions, not fly the plane.
 - great to be able to give opinion and have someone to contact if there are things that happen or if you have idea of what to do better, what's not perfect yet, what can be optimised,
 - tech roadmap, being able to name features, see what others have named, upvote
 - tech roadmap, good idea,
- Involvement level
 - large org, do not have the time for deep engagement in development and enrollment and things like that. All kinds of users/potential users included in the process, everyone has other goals and topics that are important to them, would result in a very large discussion. Afraid of not having time to spend on that. So dashboard great to have, but I think not realistic for us to be incorporated in this complex way, talking to the different stakeholders. Unfortunately, we cannot do this all the time, great to be able to give opinion and have someone to contact if there are things that happen or if you have idea of what to do better, what's not perfect yet, what can be optimised, but I do not have time to attend meetings and discussions.
 - Feedback on specifics, but not as an annual thing. Some kind of contact of course, but other than that, not a lot to do.
 - so many things we already have to attend and have opinions about, something off the shelf is preferable. We'd like to provide feedback. (Consultative not truly democratic)
 - I don't want to be just a customer, at the same time, we are oversolicited so maybe just to be able to have one time a year to meet and be informed as a democratic way of deciding on evolution etc. (Crossref, all members encouraged to vote in the election) I went last year but not enough time to stay for the whole thing. (Other side, we put in so much work to make it possible for everyone to participate and still) Yes, it's my fault, it is great that you've made it possible

Other points which came up

“What is a Crossref Event?” - many participants were not familiar with Crossref Event Data, and we will need to explain this in our documentation for BAD.

Publishers were not clear about whether they could only see data for their own titles, or whether they would be able to see other publishers' data, and compare their titles.

There was some confusion about whether publishers had to provide all the data sources or not (for example, if their content isn't on JSTOR, would they need to be on JSTOR to participate?). They also wondered about integrating Amazon and institutional repository data.

A common frustration was incomplete data, which hampered making accurate comparisons.

We wondered if the hesitation of some publishers about pricing might relate to their realisation that BAD could threaten their current job of gathering and crunching data.

Things that came up repeatedly

- What is a Crossref Event?
- Can we see other publishers' data, compare our titles to others like it or across a subject/field?
- Most download activity is tracked for closed books via kindle, can Amazon data be integrated? eg, CSV once a quarter? Or IR data, where the press has unique distribution nodes, or the author has a website?
- Does the publisher need to provide all the data sources or not? Different picture depending on who is providing the data. Eg, our content isn't on JSTOR, so would we need to be on JSTOR to participate?
- Comparing data is maddening, incomplete data
- Wonder if pull-back re: pricing might also be coming from realisation that right now, some of these folks are being paid to do the work of gathering and crunching data; could this replace their job?
- our platforms run from PKP and if we could include their data in this dashboard, that would make it a lot more interesting for us
- Defensive stance for libraries (community as protection against bad actors); missing from publishers who aren't coming from that angle
- What's possible re: geodata? City level?